

Covid – 19 Pandemic led Reverse Migration: Challenges and it's impact on Bihar Economy

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Abstract

Migration is a bigger option for earning and livelihood in Bihar either for earning and either for push-pull factors, for which people have to move other states in search of work and better wages. But Covid-19 pandemic emerged as a weakening affliction for which huge reverse migration is being noticed in the State. So this research tried to examine labour accommodate and employment opportunities in rural areas due to Covid-19 pandemic led reverse migration and to investigate the impact of Covid-19 on employment status, income profile and livelihood of returned migrants in Bihar. This research also discusses the possible measures to create some other livelihood by rebuilding the State economy after Covid-19. The relation between the migration and sustainable development is more complex the political, social and economic processes of potential destination. State will also examine how and where these migrant labourers get employment. If reverse migration is not governed properly, it can also negatively impacted on development. Both secondary and primary data are used in the research. The research found a sudden rise in labour supply with a large scale is catch sight of the State economy of Bihar. Job loss is the massive loss faced by the migrant followed by income loss. The research found that income of migrant workers, household income debarring migrants and nature of their work give indicative impact on the vulnerability of migrants.

Keywords: Employment, Job loss, Migration, Pandemic, Sustainable development goals.

Introduction:-

Covid -19 is a major threat to the livelihood and health of millions of people around the world as well as in India. This covid-19 pandemic had triggered on large scale migration in the country. The Covid-19 led migration is the second largest mass migration in India's history after the country's partition, when 14 million people were displaced (Inamdar and Thuroo, 2020). Every year a large number of people migrate move to big cities of different states to endeavor employment opportunities to earn bread and butter for their families. After the partition of India in covid-19 the country is beholding second largest mass migration. Migrant workers are normally employed in informal sectors, low-skilled risky jobs in the field of agriculture, construction and domestic work. The Periodic Labour Force Survey (PLFS) 2017-2018 shows the reckoned number of Indian workers in 2018 was 471.5 million, out of reckoned 1358 million. There were 115.0 million casual workers, 114.2 million workers are earning regular wages or salaries and 242.3 million remaining employed by self. Migration is an integral part of the Indian economy and it constitutes a significant share of the country's Gross Domestic Product (GDP). In India 194 million are employed in permanent and semi-permanent out of 482 million workers according to the 2011 Census. The pattern of India's migration is much slanted. Bihar and Uttar Pradesh constitute the highest out of migrants in India, while most of the migrated people move towards Capital city of India i.e. Delhi, Maharashtra, Gujrat etc. Bihar is one of

the economically backward States of India and Bihar is the major source of migrant workers in the country. Migrant labour is also one of the major important sources of household and livelihood in rural Bihar and also in some district urban areas of Bihar. 55% of households have atleast one migrant workers. More than 90% migrant workers work outside of Bihar. 85% working in urban areas outside Bihar, especially in manufacturing and constructional sectors. Thus, by far migrant work is so widespread in rural areas of Bihar that migrant workers came from across all households and socio economic categories. People move to other States in search jobs and better wages.

The State suffers from distress migration due to unavailability of work opportunities in the State. In Bihar Ganga river divides it in two parts in North Bihar and South Bihar. North Bihar is suffers from flood because there are many rivers in the North Bihar whereas South Bihar suffers from natural calamities like drought also there is no big industries in Bihar. As per the newspaper, media sources within the State many people from rural areas of Bihar migrated to the urban part as well as to the state capital and other big cities majorly in search of jobs

Theoretical Relations between Migration and Economy

Development theories and literature had recognized the relationship between migration and development for a long time (Srivastava et al., 2020). With complete and accurate information by the individuals about expected income of two places,

migration is economically rational and helpful for economic development (Harris & Todaro, 1970). Poor unemployed persons are forced to migrate from their home place to industrialised urban places due to structural disequilibrium in the economy. Different socio-economic reasons like marriage, in search of employment, movement of earning person, etc. are the main reason of migration (Kandhare & Bharadi, 2019). The Economic growth of the most economically advanced states in India majorly backed by the hard work put on by migrant workers (Damani et al., 2020). By the hardship work by these migrant workers, the state and the people of that state get advances in many ways (Bhagat et al., 2020; ilo Monitor, 2020). Migrant workers are identified by low paid, unskilled, deprivation of any form of social security and working in hazardous environments. According to official employment figures, the Indian factories had around 100 million internal migrant workers, with a major effect on India's economy (Deshingkar & Akter, 2009). Rural migrant workers primarily operate in temporary, characterized by low wages, job insecurity and economic vulnerability, common characteristics of informal work environments (Zeitlyn et al., 2014). Therefore, these workers are most vulnerable to any adverse situations like that Covid-19 pandemic.

Covid-19 Pandemic and Migration

The world is facing a huge economic and social crisis for Covid-19 (Asian Development Bank, 2020). Every part of the economy got pressure due to this pandemic, and among them, poor informal and migrants are the most vulnerable group (Bhagat et al., 2020; Thomas, 2020). The risk of job loss is higher for those working in the unorganized sector, and those do not have proper contracts (Khanna, 2020). It is all important for the government to facilitate adequate steps in order to mitigate the negative impact of unprecedented economic inactivity (Damani et al., 2020). That's why it is also important to take care of marginalized vulnerable groups in this critical time period. World wide more than 25 million jobs would be threatened because of the increasing spread of the coronavirus as estimated by ILO. It has been seen that many employers are terminating the employment of their employees without any prior notice or have stopped the salary of their working employees (ILO, 2020a) also some of them decrease the salary of their employees. According to the Centre for monitoring Indian Economy, over 122 million people in India lost their jobs in April 2020, majority of them small seller and wage workers. According to the Azim Premji University's Centre for sustainable employment, 80% of urban workers have lost employment, while self employed and the farmers in the non-farm field have been significantly reduced in their incomes.

Migration and Sustainability Debates

The averment of Sustainable Development included in the international political agenda in 2015 through the SDGs with eleven out of seventeen goals explicitly relevant to the migration (UN2019). Attached to these goals eleven indicates the situation of migration (Adger et al.). Including, international documents such as the Global Compact for safe, orderly and Regular Migration (UN 2018) and the issues on Migration and Sustainable Development (UNSCD 2012) examine problems associated with migration – for either receiving or host countries or for migrating individuals themselves. For, sending countries, migration has long been seen as failure of internal development, where lack of employment and infrastructure forces migrants to leave causing 'brain drain' and preventing innovation in home countries. (eg. Doquier et. al. 2007; de Haas 2010). From last two decades debates on migration have again become elation. Discussions on man power drain and brain drain have shifted notions of brain circulation and globalization of labour: there is a change in perception of migrants, from mere less skilled workers and hence financial remitters, to people with knowledge and skills (social remitters) and agents conveying these remittances, often to home and to some extent to the host country, as well (De Haas 2010; Levitt and Lamba-Nieves 2011). Migration is an integral part of society, migration is still overall framed as development issue causing problems for either host or receiving States. And challenges related to migration are highlighted in the debate of Sustainable Development. Recurring migration problems such as violation of labour rights, living conditions are not appropriate, continuing dissimilarities in access to free mobility (UN 2018) and potentials to enhance the migration situation mentioned in the SDG implementation process are certainly highly relevant. Individual migrants' rights and effects of migration on a national scale are both under debate, but often separated from each other (Delgado wiser et al. 2013; Delgado Wise 2020).

The Sustainable Development Goals recognizes that migration is a powerful driver of sustainable development for migrants and also for their communities. Migration is a transformational for these who move and for the area and economies of native and destination both. Since migration is a major reason of worldly and people's health, so migration is incorporated into planning for sustainable development. Within the SDGs, migration is recognized as 'multidimensional reality' that is of "major relevance for the development of counties of origin, transit and destination" (2030 Agenda, articles 29). Migrants are acknowledged as able to make a "positive contribution" to inclusive growth (article 29), but

the Sustainable Development Goals seems to mention mostly the interests in the country of origin the form of remittances from the international labour migrants. Remittances, to be sure play a important economic role in nations with more international migration, but with notable social consequences such as brain drain. While talking about the fulfilment of Sustainable Development Goals India has vehemently pushed for the concerns in target fixing and goals fixing. Till 2030, in India every citizen either female or male including differently abled people with disabilities would have a job which contributes to the country's GDP. To achieve this goal, The unparagoned economic crisis that abolish advancement towards Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) has been unbridle by Covid-19 pandemic. An unparagoned rise in poverty, hunger and unemployment worldwide has endangered the fault lines and structural weaknesses in the present social security regime worldwide, making of hundreds of millions of people insecurity of food and more vulnerable people to be pushed into extreme poverty. It has pushed the everyone backwards by several years by back the progress achieved towards by several years by back reversing the progress achieved towards implementing the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) to reduce poverty and hunger. United Nations Secretary General has warned in his progress report (May 2020) on the performance status of SDGs that COVID-19 crisis pandemic is pushing tens of millions of people back into extreme hunger and poverty. This pandemic crisis has also been an trial; for the India and Global media: while the extensive coverage of COVID-19 has strengthened pandemic communication measures, questions have also been arised with regard to the content, intent and attempt to limit the institutional flow of official facts related with the pandemic. Announcement of a nation-wide lockdown from the midnight of 25th March 2020 which ruib economic activities. It caused an unparagoned 'reverse' migration by millions of migrant workers form India's major urban and industrial sectors, which has wide ranging ramification for the future of Indian economy. Loss of jobs and little saving to survive in big cities such as Delhi, Mumbai etc. with transportation closed, many walked miles to their villages. There are also instances when out of desperation to comeback, many have used all their minimal belongings to their villages. Also instances of desperation to return, many have used all their savings or have to taking up new loans or even money transfers from their family members and friends. This facilitated debated around the pathetic living conditions of migrant peoples across various cities and states. It also can be assumed that the lack of support both from the government agencies and the employers have forced

the migrant labourers to return to the homestate either on by the thousands of shramik express trains run by the government or by their foot. While many of the Indian States are working relentlessly to control the spread of Covid-19 caese states such as Bihar faced a dual challenge of the Covid-19 pandemic, viz., shrinking economy and the situation of reverse migration (Ranjan et al., 2020) . the effect of the Covid-19 pandemic can be most devastating in Bihar given its demographic characteristics and socio-economic. Bihar is one of the poorest states in the country with a population size of 104 million (104,099,452 persons) which is around 8.6 percent of the total population of the country (Census 2011); and in 2020 , it can be likely to be around 128 million (128,458,570 persons). It is also specify by high population density i.e. 1102 per sq.km. limited industrialization lack of employment opportunities, and highest tendency for out migration rate, which may further combined the current situation of the state. Studies in the relation of inter-state out-migration in the poorer states in India have shown that across the various socio-economic groups, the migrants at the urban destinations are economically better placed in the Monthly Per Capita Consumption Expenditure (MPCE) wealth quintile when compared to the non-migrants/ population at the native State (Raja and Sarkar 2020, Sarkar 2019; Joe et.al. 2011). But in the present situation it can be said that the sudden loss for job of the migrants, and their spontaneous return to the native place will impact their economic security and push them towards the low levels in the MPCE lowest income distribution.

Aim/Purpose:- Aim of this research article is to discuss the possible measures to create some other livelihood by rebuilding the rural economy after Covid-19.

Objective:- Objective of this research article are:-

1. To examine labour accommodate and employment opportunities in rural areas due to COVID-19 led reverse migration.
2. To investigate the impact of Covid-19 on employment status, income profile and livelihood of returned migrants in Bihar.

Data/Method:- Method used in this research article is both quantitative and qualitative research. It is descriptive analysis. Both primary and secondary data are collected for this research article. It includes, books, journals, articles, Indian Government Reports, Bihar State Government Reports, NITI Aayog's Reports etc.

Reverse migration and its impact on Bihar Economy

The impact of reverse migration can be much higher in Bihar with respect to other Indian states given the fact that the tendency of Economic migration in the State for economic causes is highest in the country.

Since the sudden statement of the country wide Lockdown, the state has observe an influx of around 3.2 million migrants from various cities in the country (Kumar 2020). To perceive the overall impact of the reverse migration in Bihar, it is important to observe into the demographic and industrial profile of the state, the employment-unemployment scenario, labour market and dependence on remittances.

Industrial and demographic profile of Bihar The economic impact of reverse migration on Bihar economy is substantially very high. The fact that, it is one of the poorest and among the low industrialised states in the country. Bihar holds 33rd rank in the per capita GDP ranking across states and the share of labour force participation in the industry is 8% only. The work structure of the state indicates that roughly around 56% of the labour force is engaged in the industry and it is around 12% higher

than the national average (Mehrotra and Roy 2020). Further, only 8% is engaged in the industry is 15% less than the national average. According to the estimation from the Periodic Labour Force Survey (PLFS) 2017-2018 and 2018-2019, Bihar has maximum number of informal workers in the total workforce which can be approximately to be between 90-94 %. This indicate that the State government will face utmost difficulty in arising new jobs both in agriculture or industry. In table 1, a comparative demographic and industrial indicators of Bihar and in table 2, shows the Labour Force Participation Rate (LFPR) and the Worker Population Ratio (WPR) of Bihar and India. These will help us to examine the scope to which the State government is in a secure situation to tackle the reverse migration crisis in the time of Covid-19 crisis.

Table 1 : Demographic and Industrial profile.

Demographic Profile	Bihar	India
Population Density	1102per sq. km.	382 per sq. km.
Population Growth Rate (Decadal)	25.40%	17.70%
Urbanization rate	11.29%	31.16%
Literacy Rate	63.82%	74.04%
Industrial Profile		
No. of Factories in operation('000)	2.91(1.5%)	194
Persons Engaged (in'000)	1162 (0.8%)	149112
Value of Output (Rs '000)	47.69 (0.7%)	7266
Net Value added (Rs'000)	5.37 (0.5%)	1146

Source : Census 2011 and Bihar Economic Survey 2019-2020.

Implication of Reverse Migration: Unemployment, Revenue and Labour market Scenrio

On the employment front, the survey conducted by the Centre for Monitoring Indian Economy (CMIE) shows that the unemployment percentage in Bihar rose to 46.6% in month of April 2020 which is greater than the national unemployment rate of 23.5 %. Table 2 represents that after the month of April and May, the unemployment percentage started to

normalize as some easing were given to some sectors to move on economic activities. However, it is observed that even though the unemployment percentage started to come down during the month of June, July and August for Bihar it was significantly higher than the national average. The abnormal increase in unemployment percentage in Bihar can be very much added both to the 'reverse migration' and also the shrinking economy during the lockdown.

Table 2: Monthly Unemployment Percentage in 2020

Month	Bihar	India
February	10.3	7.8
March	15.4	8.8
April	46.6	23.5
May	46.2	23.5
June	19.5	11
July	12.2	7.4
August	13.4	8.3

Source : Centre for Monitoring Indian Economy (CMIE)

In table 3 the LFPR and WPR for Bihar and India. These are some of the most prominent indicators which can show the state of economic activity, employment and the performance of the overall economy. The LFPR is defined as the percentage of

is defined as the percentage of persons in the labour force in the population. It is a estimate to evaluate the working population in an economy. Lower rate of LFPR usually review poor level of economic activity and economic development. WPR is the number of persons employed per'000 population. It can be noted that Bihar has lower level of LFPR and

WPR compared to all India level for all the groups male and urban and rural.

Table : 3 LFPR and WPR (in percent)

Categories	Labour Force Participation Rate (LFPR)		Worker Population Ratio (WPR)	
	Bihar	India	Bihar	India
Rural Male	48.8	55.1	43.6	52.1
Urban Male	48.4	56.7	43.4	52.7
Rural Female	2.6	19.7	2.6	19
Urban Female	4.7	16.1	4.1	14.5

Source : PLFS (2018-2019)

The financial situation of the state has also make worse during this period. The loss of revenue for the State government stands at around 82.29% in April 2020 compared to the April 2019-2020 financial year. The revenue for the month of April fell to INR 450.21 crore from the INR 2542.23 crore in last April (Singh 2020). According to SBI Ecocurap report, 2020 the State Domestic Product (GSDP). Accordingly, the state of the Bihar has observed an estimated loss of INR 74,249 crores (11.5 percent of GSDP). Given this scenario, it can be argued that the government of Bihar is under huge financial constraint to accommodate the return migrants. It is also expected that due to the unprecedented excessive supply of labour, the wages in Bihar may fall for further which is already amongst the lowest in the country. The fall in wages will also adversely the already falling consumption demand (Source: Calculated using PLFS 2018-2019).

The return of millions of migrants workers will put huge burden on the rural labour market which has also in a very poor state of affairs and was one of the very cause for large migration rate from Bihar. The shrinking economy levels will further add to the fuel, and will make it very difficult for he employment – oriented sectors such as industry, construction, service sector, manufacturing etc., to revive. Hence, it can be assent that these who have returned to the native states may not get an instant opportunity in the existing job markets will experience several challenges given the fact that a large section of return migrants will now look for employment in the agricultural sector.

The job opportunities in the rural non-formal sector is also very loss given the fact that it largely comprises small and petty dealers, shops and business which doesn't fulfill enough employment options. In such circumstances, the rural labour markets in these poorer states may experience higher levels of unemployment, disguised unemployment, under-employment, exploitation, deterioration of working conditions etc. this may also show to substantial fall in wage rate in the State which is the lowest in the country. The only option left to those who are count job in the rural labour market is to get work via MGNRES and other employment generating schemes such as Garib

Kalyan Rojgar Yojana (GKRY). Economic Impact due to loss of Remittances Along with the fallout of overall economic health of the State due to the Covid-19 pandemic such as rising unemployment rate reduce economic activity etc., the loss of remittances may have huge negative impact in the overall economy. The unexpected loss of remittances due to the reverse migration further push the rural population towards poverty (Ranjan and Biht, 2020). According to a survey conducted by ILFS more than 505 of the households in the Bihar have migrant who moved for economic reasons (Roy et al 2020). The study shows that the dependence on remittances are very huge among the migrant households. On an average the remittances sent by a migrant is INR 26,620. Earlier surveys by NSSO 64th round migration (20007-2008) also found that the state has maximum remittances dependency in the country. In rural Bihar, among the migrant households, near about 74.5% of households have remittances this percentage is twice the national average of 36.6%. in urban Bihar, it was near about 61.4% against the national average of 24%. This way it is argue that the absence domestic remittances will also push the households towards indebtedness as approximately around 6% of the remittance getting households uses remittances for repayment of debt. Given very high dependence on remittances, it can be assert that without remittances, the demand for the consumption goods will fall. Many of the return migrants have faced severe economic challenges and have faced severe economic challenges and have undergone emotional damage during the journey back to home. That's why it can be said that these migrants will not be able to re-migrate again to the usual migration destinations. Impact of Reverse Migration on the major destination states

The major destinations for economic migrants are the greater income states that have improvement of having economic pull factors. These States have higher per capita income, higher wages, infrastructure development, employment or business opportunities in various sectors such as services, construction, manufacturing, industries etc. Empirical studies in the Indian Contexts have disclose that the richer States such as Delhi, Maharashtra, Punjab, Gujrat, etc. are the main

destination States and are the gainers of human capital etc. (Chandra Shekhar and Sharma 2014, Castaldo et al 2012; Joe et al 2011; Bhagat 2009). However, with the emergence of Covid-19 pandemic and the return of millions of migrant labourers, it is major destination s which are losing the cheap labour from the poorer States. Most of the migrant labourers from Bihar usually employed in the unorganized sectors i.e. services construction, manufacturing, domestic workers, small businesses etc. the absence of these migrant workers who already worked at various capacities in the urban areas of these states will lead to worker shortages and create bottle necks in the production process, thereby impacting the industrial and overall growth of the economy.

Table 4 : Major destinations of Bihar male migrant workers (in percent)

Months	Bihar	India
February	10.3	7.8
March	15.4	8.8
April	46.6	23.5
May	46.2	23.5
June	19.5	11
July	12.2	7.4
August	13.4	8.3

Source : D-3 Census-2011.

Table 5 : Major destinations of Bihari female migrant workers (in percent)

State	Bihar
Uttar Pradesh	16.72
Jharkhand	12.13
West Bengal	11.96
Haryana	11.39
Delhi	10.49
Punjab	9.09
Maharashtra	8.19
Gujarat	3.95
Other States	16.08

Source : D-3 Census-2011 According to Census 2011, in terms of numbers the share of inter-state migration flow Bihar is around 17.91% which is the 2nd highest after Uttar Pradesh Table 4 & Table 5 shows the major destination states for the economic migrants workers from Bihar. It is observed that for the economic migrant labourers majority of them, i.e. 17.51 % migrated to Delhi. On the other side, in case of female migrants, majority of them i.e. 16.72% migrant workers to the bordering State of Uttar Pradesh. This shows some kind of bias on the pattern selection of destination States for female and male migrant workers. However, even though the tendency to migrate and the choice of destination varies between both the groups. Also, it can be argued that as inter-state economic migrant workers from Bihar is most dominantly by the male stream with a concentration of around 92.63%. Therefore, destination States such as Delhi, West Bengal, Maharashtra, Jharkhand, etc. will be most concerned due to the absence of Bihar male migrants. **Reverse migration and problem faced by people**

The Nation wide lockdown announced on 25th March to control the spread of Covid-19 resulted in large number of job loss in both the sectors I.e. informal and formal sectors. Economic activity comes to a stand still, triggering an exodus of migrant workers from employment hubs in urban India to their native villages. Bihar alone accounted for 14.3% of over 10 million migrant workers who returned to their home states.

Over two-fifths of migrant workers surveyed stayed in the destination areas, about nine out of 10 workers reported loss of work days, and 94% reduced their remittances back home. The average fall in remittances was more than 50% significantly adding to the income shock faced by their households in native locations. (Datt, etc.al) More than 25% of the migrant workers who stayed in destination areas also reported to decrease in their remuneration rates by about a quarter on average. Reverse Migration for forced the demand for work in MGNREGS to its highest since 2013-14 in May and June also many have complains that payments in MGNREGS have delayed for months.

Intervention of Union Government and SDG impacted

SDG & LIVELIHOODS	EASING EMPLOYERS' FINANCIAL BURDEN	PF support for employees of business and organised workers	New scheme, introduced as part of PMGKIP under which Government of India contributes 12 percent of salary each on behalf of both employer and employee to EPF, will be extended by another three months. Total benefits accrued is about ₹2,500 crores to 72.22 lakh employees.
		EPF contribution reduced	Statutory contribution reduced for the employees from 12 percent to 10 percent to infuse more disposable income.
	FARMERS	KCC	25 lakh new KCC sanctioned with loan limit of ₹25,000 crore.
		Agriculture loan moratorium	Loan moratorium of three months to 3 crore farmers.
		Liquidity support	₹86,000 crore worth of loans approved between March and April 2020. Refinancing scheme started through NABARD.
	MIGRANT LABOURERS	Infrastructure support	₹1,00,000 crore for infrastructure development for farmers to sell their produce at Farm-gate.
		Shelters	States allowed to use State Disaster Relief Fund to set up shelters for migrant labourers.
	LABOURERS BENEFITS	MNREGA job card	Provision for including migrants for MGNREGA, thereby creating 14.62 crore person days.
		Labour code	Universalisation of labour code across the country for minimum wages. Statutory concept of National Floor Wage introduced and adopted. Appointment letter to all labourers. ESIC benefits for all districts of India.
		Social security	Social security for gig workers. Provisions of Social Security Fund for unorganised sector workers. Gratuity for fixed term employment.

Source : SDG Index 3.0

Conclusion

Migrant workers have been severely affected by Covid-19 pandemic and lockdown due to loss of jobs and income. As a result of this a huge reverse migration is being noticed in several States of the country and more particularly, less developed States like Bihar. The workable population increased due to huge reverse migration, for which labour supply has increased in Bihar. After returning, those people are facing many problems, one of the important of them is lack of job opportunity and many of them are working at a low wages. Those people's average monthly income has drastically declined, which is a matter of concern from the standard of living. Migrants having less income by own or by family members suffered the most in this crisis period. To overcome these problems Bihar economy needs to be revive. This can be done such as lowering income tax which will increase disposable income and encourage consumer spending. Next, is to generate employment such as MGNREGS, Gareeb Kalyan Rojgar Yojana (GKRY) and other schemes. Working days in MGNREGS should be increased. Government may take initiatives to revive the industry in Bihar so that people get work at their near by places. Government conducted skill mapping for all the migrant workers those who returned during lockdown. The migrants have been categorized into different groups namely like mechanics, health care, electrical, construction workers etc. This creates a database for the government which can be used to identify and provide required help to the migrants. This way Bihar Government need to be work to fight the impact of reverse migration.

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